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DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS OF GASTRONOMIC TOURISM IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Yusupov Ne'matillo Saidturaevich

Andijan Institute of Economics and Construction, assistant teacher of the Department
of Network Economics

Sharobiddinov Ahrorbek Qosimjon ugli

3rd grade student of the Faculty of Economics of the Andijan Institute of Economics
and Construction

ABSTRACT

Gastronomic tourism, or culinary tourism: is one of the main types of tourism, the main goal of which is to familiarize tourists with the national cuisine and food culture of that country during their trip to a certain country.

Key words: *gastrotourism, agrotourism, urban tourism, gastronomic tourism association.*

A gastronomic tourist, first of all, is considered an integral part of culture, the national and traditional dishes, the preparation process, serving methods, eating patterns and postures, while seeing and learning about the history, economy, state policy and beliefs of the local population of the traveling country. Gastronomic tourism is attracting increasing interest as a new and developing market. It attracts many tourists (or foodies) who want to try the local cuisine, and this is one of the main reasons for traveling to new and exotic places. One of the driving forces behind traveling both globally and locally is gaining an in-depth knowledge of a country's local and rural cuisine. Many local dishes are prepared according to traditional recipes that have been passed down for centuries and have become an important means of learning about the culture and heritage of the region. Gastronomic tourism is usually divided into two types:

Agrotourism, field (rural) gastronomic tourism; It is understood to see with one's own eyes the ecologically clean products (fruits and vegetables, dairy products, viticulture), harvesting or packaging of the country being traveled, and tasting the products [1-12].

Gastronomic tourism of the city involves visiting, learning and tasting enterprises that process and produce local products, eateries that prepare national dishes, food stores and other facilities. .

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 5, 2019 on additional measures for the rapid development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 5611 established the task of developing new tourism programs, taking into account promising types of tourism, including the potential of gastronomic tourism, in the regions of our country. It should be noted that the gastronomic potential of Uzbekistan is always highly appreciated by many of our foreign tourists. At the same time, our country was recognized as the winner of the best gastronomic destination in the National Geographic competition [13-30]. In addition, Uzbekistan is participating in the #SayohatErtaga gastronomic campaign organized by the initiative of the World Tourism Organization. All this shows that Uzbekistan is paying high attention to the development of gastronomic tourism.

Uzbek cuisine is notable for using more mutton, less beef and horse meat. Uzbek national dishes are among the sweetest and most diverse dishes in the world. In Eastern culture, it is customary to bring a guest to the table with various sweets, jams, and prepare sweet dishes. These customs are also very developed among the peoples of Uzbekistan. Taking into account the popularity of many Uzbek national dishes both in the East and in the West, I will give information about their role in gastronomic tourism. National dishes of Uzbekistan have a unique taste and shine among world dishes. One of them is pilaf [31-45].

According to the information of the Russian analytical agency "TurStat", Uzbekistan is among the top five in the ranking of the CIS and near foreign countries in the field of gastronomic tourism. These are Georgia, Azerbaijan, Armenia, Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan.

We know that it has always been interesting for tourists to get acquainted with the process of preparation of national dishes in the homeland of those dishes. Therefore, public organizations, in particular, the Association of Chefs of Uzbekistan, play a special role in popularizing the brand "Cuisine of Uzbekistan" on a global scale.

In order to introduce Uzbek national dishes to the world and increase the flow of tourists to our country, the Association of Chefs of Uzbekistan became a member of the Association of World Chefs Community in 2010, and the Association of Chefs of the World Islamic Countries in 2017. As a result, many foreign festivals, summits, competitions, exchanges of experience and other similar events are being participated in and high goals are being achieved.

While the current processes of economic modernization are being implemented, the main part of the economy is occupied by enterprises of the service sector. Their share in the gross domestic product, in the composition of the employed in the economy, in the taxes paid to the state budget, in the most important issues such as the

creation of new jobs is constantly increasing, and the continuation of this process in the future is strengthened by legal and regulatory documents. Implementation of the tasks defined in the decision "On measures to accelerate the development of the service sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2006-2010" announced by the first President I. Karimov in 2006 It is necessary to carry out studies on the field of presentation, including catering, its activity, its role and importance in the field of tourism, and to develop conceptual directions for the development of the field. Also, the development of the service sector has a direct impact on the welfare of our people. Catering establishments are characterized and classified according to their various characteristics [46-62].

In order to develop tourism in Uzbekistan, expand the service system for tourists and create all conditions for them, large funds are allocated for the construction of new tourist complexes, hotels, campsites, restaurants, bars, transport sectors. The development of tourism at such a pace necessarily requires the development of public catering as well, because all tourists, regardless of whether they are domestic or foreign, have to use restaurants or food chains. Otherwise, people will have to carry all the food with them or prepare and eat it at home. But tourists do not have such opportunities, therefore, they are forced to use catering services, and the existence of these conditions allows for the harmonious development of tourism. Therefore, one of the main types of services in tourism is catering service.

There is no uniform classification of catering establishments around the world. But, despite this, catering establishments of a certain type (type), which are widespread in many countries, are shown separately. There are also restaurants with national cuisine, which are famous for Italian, Chinese, Greek, Turkish, English, American, Indian, French, German restaurants. Some of them are distinguished by their very low prices, while others are distinguished by their high value. Tourists are usually interested in getting to know the cuisine of the country they are in. In many cases, the host will provide information about interesting national and inexpensive restaurants of the city, and tours will be organized to introduce national restaurants. For example, in Bavaria, tourists are treated to Bavarian (German) cuisine, namely famous white sausages and Bavarian beer. And in Munich, tourists are definitely taken to the Hofbräuhaus, the biggest beer hall. In Austria, the most famous in the world, schnitzels (a type of cutlet) are served, and of course in Italy, lunch is not complete without pasta (pasta). Afghan, Colombian, Indian, and Czech restaurants are operating in the United States and in many other countries. Recently, vegetarian restaurants have started to appear, or Jewish restaurants have also been operating.

The most famous dishes of Uzbek cuisine are pilaf, manti, dolma, hasip, mutton kebab, somsa and tandir bread. At the same time, this or that dish is prepared differently in different regions of the country. For example, Fergana pilaf is completely different from Samarkand. The preparation of the same dishes in different ways dates back to

the times of the Great Silk Road. At that time, Uzbek cities received many merchants from Asia. A mixture of traditions, customs, new national dishes and, most importantly, spices, turned each ancient city into a unique culinary center.

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In particular, in 2018, Uzbekistan won the first place in the "Gastronomic tourism" category at the "National Geographic Traveler" award held by the "National Geographic" magazine.

On August 6, 2019, the Gastronomic Tourism Association of Uzbekistan opened its doors. The event dedicated to this event was held in the meeting hall of the Association of Chefs of Uzbekistan with the participation of representatives of the ministries and agencies of the republic, mass media of the country. , organization of forums, seminars, scientific conferences, roundtables, contests and other events, as well as implementation of this field. various projects that contribute to the development of tourism. Officials say that in order to extend the tourist season in our country, the Association regularly holds the international festival of national dishes "Lazzat Uzbekistan" in November every year, attracts international travel agencies and organizes regional gastronomic tours throughout Uzbekistan.

According to the chairman of the association, Gulnoza Odilova, the "Museum of Uzbek National Gastronomy" has been established in Uzbekistan, which will provide a wide range of Uzbek national cuisine and its history for foreign tourists. The museum also hosts international scientific conferences and presentations for the country's tourism agencies.

At the opening ceremony, the Association spoke about its purpose, activities and terms of membership, and provided information about restaurants, cafes, catering establishments in our Republic.

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